

Why the Goldbach Conjecture is likely true

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Abstract

In this paper we break each even number $2N$ into 2 intervals centered at N . We then count the number of primes on either side that pair up symmetrically with either non-prime numbers or primes on the other side, calling them *1-primes* and *2-primes* for each even number $2N$, with *2-primes* being *Goldbach Prime Pairs (GPPs)*. By running a Python program on even numbers upto 100,000 we show that while the number of 2-primes and 1-primes oscillate with local peaks and troughs, their moving averages over very small intervals stabilise and follow a $1/Ln(N)$ curve, similar to primes. This strongly suggests that not only is the *Goldbach Conjecture* true but the number of *Goldbach* primes for each even numbers follows, on average, an increasing curve proportional to $N/Ln(N)$. We find the constant of proportionality to be 0.19 for 2-prime pairs and 0.81 for 1-prime pairs.

(We wish to thank our dad, Nasir Afaf, for proof reading the paper and suggesting stylistic changes especially with the abstract and introducing us to moving averages. This paper would have been messier without his feedback.)

1 Background

In June 2022, when one of us (Ismael) was in Year 10, the Computer Science teacher at Tonbridge School at the time, Mr Robertson, told the class about a conjecture called the *Collatz Conjecture*. The *Collatz Conjecture* takes a number and depending on whether it is odd or even applies a conditional rule to it. If an even number x is input the rule is to return $\frac{x}{2}$. If the input number x is odd the rules returns $3x + 1$. Mr Robertson

said if the output was then used as input for the next step, and so on, a sequence of numbers would emerge where any starting number would always reach 1 and as a result start looping between 4, 2 and 1. He then asked the class to write a Python program which would choose different starting numbers and list the sequence of numbers generated until 1 was reached.

After Ismael programmed it up, he decided to show Mikki, who is also his 10 year old brother, and loved programming up games using MIT's Scratch programming language. Mikki taught himself programming when around 7 years of age. During Covid lockdowns in 2020 and 2021, at age 8 and 9, he programmed up hundreds of games and even got a bit into the C Sharp programming language when Scratch was not precise enough for his needs. Mikki loves games where some unexpected patterns or dynamics emerge from simple rules. He is always tinkering with the games he programs up.

Mikki loved the *Collatz Conjecture* and the fact that every sequence always seemed to eventually reach 1 in a similar final end trajectory of 4,2 and 1.

A few days later our Dad asked Ismael what he had told Mikki. It turned out that while on a walk in the park with our Dad, Mikki could not stop talking about the *Collatz Conjecture* and worked out sequences for many starting numbers as they chatted along. Our Dad said Mikki even started coming up with other versions where you don't multiply odd numbers by 3 but other numbers etc resulting in different end patterns that always converged. Our Dad asked if Ismael could program this up for Mikki but Ismael never got the time to do it.

In early December 2022, because of train strikes all over the UK our Dad had to drive both of us to different schools in different directions on long trips. One such morning at around 7 am, on the long drive to school in our van, Ismael vaguely remembered the *Goldbach Conjecture (GC)* which he thought might entertain Mikki. Ismael could not remember what the exact conjecture was so he verbally asked Google about it. Google said *GC* conjectures that every even number greater than 2 can be expressed as the sum of two prime numbers.

We both found this very interesting and in the 10 minutes or so before we got to Tonbridge, we began to experiment with different even numbers. We both started finding what we will now call *Goldbach Prime Pairs (GPPs)* for small even numbers we could think of so we could do quick calculation in our heads. While doing this we noticed Mikki was finding these *GPPs* by trying to find primes close to the middle of the even number. We describe his method in the next section.

2 Mikki's Method

To show Mikki's Method we use an example for the even number 20. Mikki started by splitting 20 into two 10s and then (e.g. $20 = 10 + 10$) from there he went to the next odd numbers up and down from the centre number (e.g. $20 = 9 + 11$). He continued doing this until both numbers were prime (e.g. $7 + 13$). He seemed to find *GPPs* very quickly using this. In fact, he quickly jumped to the conclusion that there would be a lot of *GPPs* for every even number rather than just the minimum 1 that the *Goldbach Conjecture* states.

Mikki wanted Ismael to program this up when he returned from school, but Ismael was busy with GCSE mocks and also very tired. Finally, on Feb 16, 2023, during half term break, Ismael agreed to program it up in Python.

3 Computation Approach

While programming, Ismael decided to break every even number into 3 different categories in terms of pairs. First were those pairs where neither number was a prime. Second, were those pairs where one number was a prime, but the other one was not. Finally the 3rd category were pairs where both numbers were prime or *GPPs*. As an example, for the number 40, the pair (15, 25) are both non prime, while the pair (13, 27) had one prime, while (11, 29) were both prime. It was clear that in each pair, each number had to be equidistant from the centre of 40. Ismael decided to calculate for each even number, $2N$, how many pairs were *NonPrime* ($0P$), how many were *OnePrime* ($1P$), and how many were *TwoPrimes* ($2P$). It is clear that *GPPs* were the same as *TwoPrimes* ($2P$)

Mikki felt that there would be more ($2Ps$) than ($1Ps$) from the examples he had done with small even numbers. Ismael felt that even if there were less so, but they did not taper out, we could see that the *GC* was likely true. Ismael conjectured that if the ratio of the numbers of ($2Ps$) to ($1Ps$) did not keep decreasing there was a strong likelihood that *Goldbach Conjecture* was true. Ismael felt that there could be an asymptotic convergence to a number > 0 . If so, the *GC* would likely be true even if we could not prove it.

Mikki, who loves art and painting, was very excited and called it the "*Birdies Conjecture*" as shown in his drawing below

In the figure above, the bird sits at the number N while its wings span equal distances to the left and right. The wing tips end on odd numbers (except for the even number 4), which may be prime or non prime. It is easy to see that every prime number will always pair up with an odd number which may be prime or not. The question is whether for even number, $2N$, there are birds sitting at N where both wing tips end at

Figure 1: Every even number $2N$ has a bird body at N and wings that end at either both non prime numbers (non-prime birdies), or just 1 prime and 1 non prime (single prime birdies), or on a pair of primes (double prime birdies). For Mikki, the GC conjecture is the same as saying there are always double prime birdies for each number N , where the body of the bird is.

prime numbers. Mikki called these "double prime birdies" and was convinced there would be many for each number N . Since we know there will always be many "single prime birdies", as prime number keep increasing with N , we just had to check how the ratio of "double prime birdies" to "single prime birdies" evolved. If "single prime birdies" kept increasing in proportion to "double prime birdies" the Goldbach Conjecture would likely be false.

The next section shows the results of the Python program.

4 Results

What we found is that the proportion of $2P$ to $1P$ oscillates with local peaks at every 3rd even number. Overall the trend was that $2P$ to $1P$ decreases but seems to approach a constant ratio on average. It seems that if we average over the last 10 or so numbers in terms of moving average we get very stable ratios.

The Figure below shows the number of 0-prime pairs, 1-prime pairs, and 2-prime pairs trends with increasing even numbers, with the x -axis being the list of even numbers.

In the figure below, we now look at the number of total primes, 1-primes, and 2-primes. There is again a trend upwards, but for 1-primes and 2-primes we see the same type of oscillations we saw in the previous figure. But it is fairly clear to see that the average number of 1-primes and 2-primes increases:

In the figure below, we now look at the percentage of primes, 1-primes, and 2-primes upto any given even number.

Figure 2: Here we see how total number of 0-prime pairs, 1-prime pairs and 2-prime pairs increase on average with each even number $2N$. Note that since they oscillate around the trend, the lines are a bit blurry as Excel cannot resolve the picture over large number of points.

Figure 3: Note that the average number of 1-primes and 2-primes increases with each successive even number, even if the actual value oscillates around an increasing mean.

Figure 4: The percentage of primes, 1-primes, and 2-primes upto any given even number decreases with a slowing rate. The percentage of 1-primes and 2-primes again oscillates but their average shows the rate of decrease also slows

Figure 5: In this graph we look at both the running average and moving average (taken over 100 points) of the ratio of 2-primes to total primes for each even number. Because of the averaging a clear graph emerges showing a rate of decrease very similar to that for the primes themselves (see previous figure)

Figure 6: In this graph we look at both the running average and moving average (taken over 100 points) of the ratio of 2-primes to 1-primes for each even number. Because of the averaging a clear graph emerges showing a rate of decrease very similar to that for the primes themselves (see previous figure)

Figure 7: Tail end of prime type counts shows local peaks every 3rd number in 1-primes with a corresponding local trough in 2-primes as they seem to exchange their counts with each other. This oscillation pattern very quickly smooths out with even a very small number of points for moving averages.

Figure 8: Here we compare the ratio of Number of Primes to Even Integers with Moving Averages of ratio of 1-primes and 2-primes to the same, plotted next to $1/\ln(N)$. Note that we took moving averages of 1-prime ratios and 2-prime ratios over 10 points each to smooth out the curves. We can see how all the curves follow the $1/\ln(N)$ shape. In fact, we could numerically see that, asymptotically, ratio of 1-prime moving average settles at approximately $0.81 \times (\text{Ratio of Primes to Ints})$ and ratio of 2-prime moving average settles to approximately $0.19 \times (\text{Ratio of Primes to Ints})$. This suggests to us that 2-primes continue to exist for all even numbers, growing at an average rate 0.19 times that for Primes

5 Conclusion

By running a Python program on even numbers upto 100,000 we showed that based on Mikki's Method while the number of 2-primes and 1-primes oscillate with local peaks and troughs, their moving averages over very small intervals stabilise and follow a $1/Ln(N)$ curve, similar to primes. This strongly suggests that not only is the *Goldbach Conjecture* true but the number of *Goldbach* primes for each even numbers follows, on average, an increasing curve proportional to $N/Ln(N)$. We find the constant of proportionality to be 0.19 for 2-prime pairs and 0.81 for 1-prime pairs.

$$N_P \propto \frac{N}{ln(N)} \quad (1)$$

$$\langle N_{1P} \rangle \propto 0.81 \frac{N}{ln(N)} \quad (2)$$

$$\langle N_{2P} \rangle \propto 0.19 \frac{N}{ln(N)} \quad (3)$$

Where $\langle \rangle$ denotes a moving average.